

The Analysis and Modeling of Voltage Survivability in Power Systems

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Abstract—The introduction of load-side control actions, to implement smart grid functions or integrate distributed generation units, has created a new source for power system dynamic events. Such events can have the capacity to adversely impact the stability in power systems. The growing interests in load-side control actions mandate the analysis and modeling of their contribution to voltage and frequency dynamics in power systems. This paper presents the analysis, development, and testing of a voltage-survivability based method for modeling the contributions of load-side control actions to power system voltage dynamics and stability. The developed method is structured using a voltage-survivability index Γ_V that is defined at bus in terms of the difference in reactive power injection before and after a load-side control action. The boundary values of the index Γ_V are derived in order to identify survivable and non-survivable load-side control actions. The voltage-survivability based method is implemented and tested for the Barbados power system. Performance tests are conducted for integrating distributed generation units, as well as implementing demand response at several load buses. Results of conducted tests demonstrate the ability of voltage-survivability based method to accurately model and quantify the impacts of load-sides activities on the bus voltages in the test power system.

Index Terms—Power system transients, power system stability, load-side control actions, distributed generation units, and smart grid functions

I. INTRODUCTION

A. General

The conventional terminology of power system stability encompasses the voltage stability, frequency stability, and inter-area oscillations [1]–[4]. Such a definition of power system stability has been utilized in the design power system controls (the primary, secondary, and tertiary) and stabilizers that can initiate responses to restore power system steady state conditions post undesired transient events [5]–[8]. Power system controls and stabilizers have been through numerous improvements to benefit from the advancements in instrumentation, communication, signal processing, digital control, and power electronic systems. Moreover, the improvements in power system controls and stabilizers have been mandated to address the continuous growth of power systems, both in power generation (capacity and diversity) and load demands [9]–[12].

The recent trends in power system operation have been in favor of adapting the de-regulated operation, which has been found effective for improving the reliability, power quality, economic operation, and sustainability [13]–[16]. In addition, many power systems have adapted the de-regulated operation mode to facilitate the dispatch of conventional and distributed generation units, while implementing load-side control activities [17]–[20]. In general, the objective of load-side control activities is to adjust power demands by means of smart grid functions (e.g. demand response, peak-demand management, etc.) and/or integrating energy storage units. These activities are typically

performed over finite time intervals, and can be presented as events with no changes in the configuration of a power system (no loss of transmission lines, generators, transformers, etc.). Such a nature of load-side control activities makes the modeling of their impacts outside the scope of power system stability analysis [21]–[24].

B. Review of Modeling and Analyzing Voltage Stability

Modern operation and control schemes for power systems have been shifting toward the generation mixes (conventional and distributed), controllable load demands, micro-grids, and sustainable energy production [1]–[4]. The implementation of such schemes has been accompanied by the deployment of advanced digital data communication, storage, and processing, including new designs of high-precision, high sampling-rate, and synchronized measurements provided by Phasor Measurement Units (PMUs) [9]–[12]. Such changes in power systems have motivated changes in the control, stability, and planning of power systems due to new types of transient events (created by generation mixes), growing number of grid-connected power electronic converters, and increasing levels of bi-directional power flows [25]–[28].

The widely used approach to model a dynamic event in a power system is the swing equation, which can be stated for generator (PV) and load (PQ) buses [7]–[10]. A dynamic event in a power system is typically triggered by an abrupt change in the active power, reactive power, and/or system configuration [20]–[23]. Such events and their impacts are analyzed through the power system stability analysis, where various methods for estimating the frequency and voltage are employed. The literature reports various methods that have been introduced for performing the power system stability analysis [12], [13]. The energy boundary surface, transient energy, direct transient method (using Lyapunov functions), eigenvalues (based on QR transformation), and unstable equilibrium point are among the popular methods for power system stability analysis [14]–[17]. The applications of these methods include the design of power system stabilizers, automatic voltage regulators, governor controls, and frequency controllers. Outcomes of power system stability analysis have been used to select settings for protection and control devices, such as the critical clearing times, pick-up values for various protective relays, and optimal placement of static VAR compensators [29]–[32].

The estimation of bus voltages (part of power system stability analysis) is usually performed using several methods, including:

- i) the bus sensitivity factors [5];
- ii) the P-V and Q-V curves [8];
- iii) the Q-V modal analysis method [9];
- iv) the minimum singular value [33];
- v) the system eigenvalues [7].

The static analysis is performed by selecting a critical operating point, and examining boundary conditions and factors that contribute to voltage stability analysis. The static analysis approach has been popular due to its simple structure, and reduced computations. Nonetheless, this approach may suffer low accuracy for systems that have non-linear loads or distributed generation units [34]–[37]. The V-P curve method utilizes a continued power flow to examine limits of the active power variation before voltage collapse or voltage instability [8], [9]. The V-P curve method has been integrated in many stability analysis tools, and become an effective approach for setting limits on loading levels to avoid voltage stability issues [11]–[14]. The Q-V curve method is based on the relationship between the reactive power injection and voltage at any bus in a power system. Using this method, a power system has voltage stability issues if one bus has its voltage decreasing with increase in the reactive power injected into that bus [38]–[41]. The Q-V curve method defines the voltage stability for a power system as the power system with all its buses having positive Q-V sensitivity [5], [6]. The main challenge for using this method is due to the difficulty in computing the Q-V curves for all buses, especially for systems with a large number of buses [42]–[45].

The Q-V modal analysis is based on determining the eigen values and eigen vectors of the reduced Jacobian matrix of the considered power system. Each determined eigen value and its corresponding right and left eigen vectors, define the mode of Q-V response. The critical mode of voltage stability is identified based on performing the Q-V sensitivity at minimum eigen value [46]. Despite its accuracy and applicability, the Q-V modal analysis can involve significant computations [1]–[4]. The minimum singular value method is also based on the Jacobian matrix of the considered power system. Using this method, a bus can have a critical voltage stability mode, when it causes the minimum singular value of the Jacobian to become of a zero value [47]–[50]. The minimum singular value method has been found accurate in identifying weak buses that can contribute to voltage instability [51]–[54].

Existing methods of voltage stability in power systems have been developed for the stability analysis, which considers system-wide transient events. Such events are usually characterized by short durations and impulse superimposed components on voltages and/or currents [1]–[6]. The adaptation of the de-regulated operation has introduced new type of power systems events, which can trigger dynamic conditions attributed to [13]:

- i) load-side control actions (smart grid functions);
- ii) variations in the power generated by distributed units.

Unlike system-wide events, the aforementioned events do not trigger transient changes in the active and/or reactive powers or changes in system configuration [55]–[58]. These new events in power systems mandate a new approach to analyze their impacts on power systems, in particular on bus voltages.

C. Article Objectives and Contributions

The previous review suggests that system-wide transient events are addressed by power system stability analyses [1]–[4]. Load side activities (load control and/or distributed generation) require a new approach to analyze their impacts on the voltage stability. The development of such an analysis method is main focus of this article, whose objectives are:

- to model the impacts of load side actions on the voltage stability;
- to introduce voltage survivability analysis to assess impacts of load side actions;
- to define a new voltage survivability index as a planning tool for load side actions.

Achieving these objectives supports the following contributions:

- 1) The development of mathematical models for voltage dynamics triggered by load side actions.
- 2) The formulation of a voltage survivability analysis for power systems.
- 3) The development and testing of an algorithm to determine the voltage survivability index $\mathbf{\Gamma}_V$.

II. MODELING DYNAMIC EVENTS IN A POWER SYSTEM

A. Generic Modeling of Power System Conditions

The generic models of any power system are typically composed as a combination of sub-models for its elements, such as generators, transmission lines, transformers, loads, etc. References [10]–[12] use a dynamic model (ϑ) for bus g (applicable for a PV or a PQ bus) that can be expressed as [12]:

$$\vartheta_g = \begin{cases} \dot{y}_g = e_g(y_g, \mathbf{V}_g, \mathbf{Y}_g, u_g) \\ \bar{S}_g = r_g(y_g, \mathbf{V}_g, \mathbf{Y}_g) \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

where $g = 1, 2, \dots, G$, y_g is the state of bus g , $\dot{y}_g = dy_g/dt$, \mathbf{V}_g is the phasor voltage of bus g , \mathbf{Y}_g is the vector containing elements of the g^{th} row in the \mathbf{Y} -bus matrix, u_g is the control action applied to bus g , $\bar{S}_g = P_g + jQ_g$, is the apparent power injected into bus g , and $e_g(\cdot)$ and $r_g(\cdot)$ are functions specified for each bus depending on its type [7]. The power balance of a steady-state condition can be formulated as [10]–[12]:

$$([\mathbf{Y}] \times [\mathbf{V}])^* \circ [\mathbf{V}] - [\bar{S}] = 0 \quad (2)$$

where $*$ is the element-wise complex conjugate operator, and \circ is the element-wise multiplication operator. The vectors $[\mathbf{V}]$ and $[\bar{S}]$ are $[G \times 1]$ vectors of \mathbf{V}_g and \bar{S}_g , respectively. A steady-state condition is declared for a power system, if the following conditions are satisfied for all buses:

$$\begin{aligned} 0 &= e_g(y_g^*, \mathbf{V}_g^*, \mathbf{Y}_g^*, 0) \\ \bar{S}_g^* &= r_g(y_g^*, \mathbf{V}_g^*, \mathbf{Y}_g^*) \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

where y_g^* , \mathbf{V}_g^* , \mathbf{Y}_g^* , and \bar{S}_g^* are associated with a steady-state condition. For a steady-state, stability actions u_g are set as $u_g = 0$ (no actions applied to bus g), as $\dot{y} = 0$. In general, the widely used approach to determine y_g^* , \mathbf{V}_g^* , and \bar{S}_g^* is the power flow analysis [8], [9]. The determination of y_g^* , \mathbf{V}_g^* , and \bar{S}_g^* (using the power flow analysis) allows using them as initial conditions for equations (1) and (2) to satisfy equation (3) [1].

The solution of equation (2) may provide more than one solution. In order to identify a unique solution for equation (2), determined values of \mathbf{V} and/or \bar{S} (using the power flow analysis) can be constrained by the power system reliability, power system stability, and economic dispatch [10]–[12]. In case of a transient event, various control and/or protection actions are initiated to ensure regaining a steady-state condition as:

$$\begin{aligned} 0 &= e_g(\tilde{y}_g, \tilde{\mathbf{V}}_g, \tilde{\mathbf{Y}}_g, 0) \\ \tilde{\bar{S}}_g &= r_g(\tilde{y}_g, \tilde{\mathbf{V}}_g, \tilde{\mathbf{Y}}_g) \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

where \tilde{y}_g , \tilde{V}_g , \tilde{Y}_g , and \tilde{S}_g are values associated with a steady-state condition, which is the result of applying stabilizing actions u_g at bus g [10]–[12].

B. Modeling Voltage Dynamics

Power system buses (PV and PQ buses) can experience voltage dynamics due to various causes, among which are the changes in injected active and/or reactive powers. The voltage dynamics at bus g can be modeled as [59]–[62]:

$$\frac{dV_g}{dt} = \frac{Q_{Dg}}{V_g} + \sum_{\substack{m=1 \\ m \neq g}}^G V_g (Y_{gm} \cos(\theta_g - \theta_m)) \quad (5)$$

where Q_{Dg} is the reactive power demands at bus g , Y_{gm} is the mutual admittance between bus g and bus m [1]. It should be noted that V_g in equation (5) represents the magnitude of bus g voltage (i.e. $V_g = |\bar{V}_g|$). The apparent power injected at bus g can be stated as [10]–[12]:

$$\bar{S}_g = \sum_{m=1}^G \bar{V}_m (\bar{V}_g \bar{Y}_{gm})^*, \text{ with } \bar{Y}_{gm} = \frac{1}{Z_{gm}} \quad (6)$$

Equation (5) and (6) can be expanded to model a power system with G buses as:

$$\begin{bmatrix} \dot{V}_1 \\ \dot{V}_2 \\ \vdots \\ \dot{V}_G \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} H_1 \\ H_2 \\ \vdots \\ H_G \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} \alpha_1 \\ \alpha_2 \\ \vdots \\ \alpha_G \end{bmatrix} \quad (7)$$

$$\begin{bmatrix} \bar{S}_1 \\ \bar{S}_2 \\ \vdots \\ \bar{S}_G \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \beta_1 \\ \beta_2 \\ \vdots \\ \beta_G \end{bmatrix} \quad (8)$$

where:

$$H_g = \frac{Q_{Dg}}{V_g} \quad (9)$$

$$\alpha_g = \sum_{\substack{m=1 \\ m \neq g}}^G Y_{gm} V_g \cos(\theta_g - \theta_m) \quad (10)$$

$$\beta_g = \sum_{m=1}^G \bar{V}_m (\bar{V}_m Y_{gm})^* \quad (11)$$

Equations (7) and (8) allow stating the functions $e(\cdot)$ and $r(\cdot)$ for G -bus power system as:

$$\dot{\mathbf{Y}} = \mathbf{H} + \boldsymbol{\alpha} \quad (12)$$

$$\bar{\mathbf{S}} = \boldsymbol{\beta} \quad (13)$$

where $\dot{\mathbf{Y}}$ and $\bar{\mathbf{S}}$ are given as:

$$\dot{\mathbf{Y}} = [\dot{V}_1, \dot{V}_2, \dots, \dot{V}_G]^T \quad (14)$$

$$\bar{\mathbf{S}} = [\bar{S}_1, \bar{S}_2, \dots, \bar{S}_G]^T \quad (15)$$

It should be noted that bold letters are used for vector variables.

III. VOLTAGE SURVIVABILITY ANALYSIS

The survivability analysis for any system addresses that system's ability to recover its steady-state functionality post a dynamic or a transient change [63]–[67]. For a power system, the survivability analysis can be related to the stability and/or reliability analyses. In these analyses, the interest is focused on the ability of a power system to regain a stable condition post transient events [11], [12].

A. Voltage Survivability of a Power System

The concept of survivability can be applied to a power system using equation (1), which indicates the initiation of actions in response to an event ρ . The application of the survivability to a power system can be mathematically stated as [1], [11]:

$$[\dot{y}] \xrightarrow{X(\rho)} 0 \text{ and } [\bar{S}] \xrightarrow{X(\rho)} [\bar{S}^*] \quad (16)$$

where $X(\rho)$ is a set of actions in response to the event ρ , as:

$$X(\rho) = [x_1(\rho), x_2(\rho), \dots, x_G(\rho)]^T \quad (17)$$

Examples of actions in the set $X(\rho)$ include shedding loads, connecting/disconnecting storage systems, adjusting active and reactive power generation, disconnecting transmission lines, etc. [1], [10]–[12]. Details for examples are discussed and thoroughly modeled in refs. [16] and [17]. The set of actions $X(\rho)$ can be initiated based on the stability analysis. Using the stability analysis, actions in $X(\rho)$ are set to ensure $[\dot{y}] \rightarrow 0$ and $[\bar{S}] \rightarrow [\bar{S}^*]$ [10]–[13]. In some cases, the post event steady-state condition may not be the same as the pre-event steady-state condition, where $[\bar{S}] \neq [\bar{S}^*]$ [10]–[13].

The difference between pre-event and post event steady-state conditions can be expressed for bus g as:

$$\begin{aligned} 0 &= e_g(\tilde{y}_g, \tilde{V}_g, \tilde{Y}_g, 0) \\ \tilde{S}_g &= \bar{S}_g^* + r_{1g}(\tilde{y}_g, \tilde{V}_g, \tilde{Y}_g, 0) \end{aligned} \quad (18)$$

where the function $r_{1g}(\cdot)$ depends on the type of bus g and $x_g(\rho)$ that is initiated in response to event ρ . The statement of equation (18) suggests two possibilities as [1]:

- If $X(\rho)$ ensures $[\bar{S}] \rightarrow [\bar{S}^*]$, then $X(\rho)$ achieves the stability and survivability of the power system.
- If $X(\rho)$ ensures $[\bar{S}] \rightarrow [\bar{S}^*]$, then $X(\rho)$ may achieve the stability (not survivability) of the power system.

B. The Voltage Survivability Index

Various types of events ρ can take place in any power system, and lead to $\dot{y} \neq 0$. In order to regain a steady-state condition, an event ρ is responded to by a set of actions X to achieve $\dot{y} \rightarrow 0$ [68]–[71]. A set of actions X involves adjustments of P and/or Q injections in several buses of a power system. The adjustments in P and Q injections (created by X) lead to a post event condition [72]–[75].

The dependence of a post event condition on the set of actions X indicates that adjustments in P and/or Q can lead to:

- Achieving stability and survivability as:

$$\bar{S}_g^* = \tilde{S}_g \left(\text{i.e. } r_{1g}(\tilde{y}_g, \tilde{V}_g, \tilde{Y}_g) = 0; \forall g \right) \quad (19)$$

- Achieving stability only as:

$$\tilde{S}_g^* \neq \tilde{S}_g \quad (\text{i.e. } r_{1g}(\tilde{y}_g, \tilde{\mathbf{V}}_g, \tilde{\mathbf{Y}}_g) \neq 0; \neg \forall g) \quad (20)$$

where $\neg \forall$ denotes "not for all".

Equations (19) and (20) indicate that power system survivability (including voltage survivability) is related to the difference between \tilde{S}_g^* and \tilde{S}_g ; $g = 1, \dots, G$. In ref. [1], a survivability index Γ is defined to quantify power system survivability, where the focus is on the frequency survivability. In this article, a voltage survivability index ($\mathbf{\Gamma}_V$) is proposed, and is defined for bus g as:

$$(\mathbf{\Gamma}_V)_g = \frac{1}{\tau} \int_t (\mathbf{Im} \{\beta_g^*\} - \mathbf{Im} \{\beta_g\}) dt \quad (21)$$

where τ is the time interval from the beginning to the end of an event, and $\mathbf{Im}(\cdot)$ is the imaginary part. Substituting equation (11) in equation (21) yields:

$$\begin{aligned} (\mathbf{\Gamma}_V)_g &= \frac{1}{\tau} \int_t \mathbf{Im} \left\{ \sum_{m=1}^G \bar{V}_g^* (\bar{V}_m^* Y_{gm}^*)^* \right\} dt \\ &\quad - \frac{1}{\tau} \int_t \mathbf{Im} \left\{ \sum_{m=1}^G \bar{V}_g (\bar{V}_m Y_{gm})^* \right\} dt \end{aligned} \quad (22)$$

The magnitude and phase of each bus voltage, along with the frequency, are typically provided as sampled measurements with a sampling time of Δt . These discrete values of \mathbf{V} , θ , and f support stating a discretized version of equation (22) as:

$$\begin{aligned} (\mathbf{\Gamma}_V)_g &= \frac{1}{2\pi\tau} \sum_{n=1}^N \sum_{m=1}^G V_g^*[n] V_m^*[n] Y_{gm}^* \sin(\lambda_{gm}[n]) \\ &\quad - \frac{1}{2\pi\tau} \sum_{n=1}^N \sum_{m=1}^G V_g[n] V_m[n] Y_{gm}[n] \sin(\lambda_{gm}[n]) \end{aligned} \quad (23)$$

where $n \in \mathbb{Z}$, $N\Delta t = \tau$, and λ_{gm} is:

$$\lambda_{gm}[n] = \lambda_m[n] - \lambda_g[n] + \theta_{gm}[n]$$

with λ_m being the phase of \bar{V}_m , λ_g being the phase of \bar{V}_g , and θ_{gm} being the phase of \bar{Y}_{gm} . The voltage survivability index can be formulated for a G -bus power system as:

$$\mathbf{\Gamma}_V = \sum_{g=1}^G (\mathbf{\Gamma}_V)_g \quad (24)$$

C. Boundary Values of $\mathbf{\Gamma}_V$

The expression in equation (21) suggests that $(\mathbf{\Gamma}_V)_g$ is [1]:

$$(\mathbf{\Gamma}_V)_g = 0 \implies \text{bus } g \text{ experiences stability and survivability}$$

$$(\mathbf{\Gamma}_V)_g \neq 0 \implies \text{bus } g \text{ may experience stability only}$$

In order to examine the boundary values of $(\mathbf{\Gamma}_V)_g$, β_g can be stated with a small change $\delta\beta_g$ as:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{Im} \{\beta_g + \delta\beta_g\} &= \sum_{m=1}^G V_g (V_m + \delta V_m) (Y_{gm} + \delta Y_{gm}) \sin(\lambda_{gm}) \\ &\quad + \sum_{m=1}^G \delta V_g (V_m + \delta V_m) (Y_{gm} + \delta Y_{gm}) \sin(\lambda_{gm}) \end{aligned} \quad (25)$$

It should be noted that equation (25) is stated with the assumption $\delta\lambda_{gm} \cong 0$. Equation (25) can be simplified as:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{Im} \{\delta\beta_g\} &= \sum_{m=1}^G V_g V_m \delta Y_{gm} \sin(\lambda_{gm}) \\ &\quad + \sum_{m=1}^G V_g \delta V_m Y_{gm} \sin(\lambda_{gm}) \\ &\quad + \sum_{m=1}^G \delta V_g V_m Y_{gm} \sin(\lambda_{gm}) \end{aligned} \quad (26)$$

The expression in equation (26) is obtained using the following:

$$\mathbf{Im} \{\beta_g\} = \sum_{m=1}^G V_m V_g Y_{gm} \sin(\lambda_{gm}) \quad (27)$$

$$0 \cong \sum_{m=1}^G \delta V_m \delta V_g (Y_{gm} + \delta Y_{gm}) \sin(\lambda_{gm}) \quad (28)$$

$$0 \cong \sum_{m=1}^G \delta V_m V_g \delta Y_{gm} \sin(\lambda_{gm}) \quad (29)$$

$$0 \cong \sum_{m=1}^G V_m \delta V_g \delta Y_{gm} \sin(\lambda_{gm}) \quad (30)$$

Equation (26) allows stating boundary values for $(\mathbf{\Gamma}_V)_g$ as:

$$\left((\mathbf{\Gamma}_V)_g \right)_{\max} \leq \mathbf{Im} \{\delta\beta_g\} \quad (31)$$

$$\left((\mathbf{\Gamma}_V)_g \right)_{\min} \geq -\mathbf{Im} \{\delta\beta_g\} \quad (32)$$

The boundary values of $(\mathbf{\Gamma}_V)_g$ (equations (31) and (32)) indicate that the stability and survivability can be achieved by a set of actions X if it can maintain the value of $(\mathbf{\Gamma}_V)_g$ as:

$$(\mathbf{\Gamma}_V)_g \in \left[\left((\mathbf{\Gamma}_V)_g \right)_{\min}, \left((\mathbf{\Gamma}_V)_g \right)_{\max} \right] \quad (33)$$

The values of $\left((\mathbf{\Gamma}_V)_g \right)_{\max}$ and $\left((\mathbf{\Gamma}_V)_g \right)_{\min}$ in equations (31) and (32) reveal their dependence on the mutual admittances between bus g and other buses. Bus g will have its $\left((\mathbf{\Gamma}_V)_g \right)_{\max} \rightarrow \infty$, if it has connections with every bus in the considered power system. This nature of $\left((\mathbf{\Gamma}_V)_g \right)_{\max}$ indicates that radially connected buses tend to have $\left((\mathbf{\Gamma}_V)_g \right)_{\max} \rightarrow 0$, thus load-side activities on such buses may yield voltage unsurvivabilities.

IV. IMPLEMENTING THE VOLTAGE SURVIVABILITY ANALYSIS

A. Voltage Survivability Analysis

The calculation of the voltage survivability index $(\mathbf{\Gamma}_V)_g$ (as in equation (23)) mandates values of \mathbf{Y} -bus matrix, bus voltages (magnitudes and phases), and frequency before and during an event ρ . Before an event, the \mathbf{Y} -bus matrix and bus voltages are determined by a power flow analysis. During an event, the \mathbf{Y} -bus matrix, bus voltages, and frequency are determined by a numerical solution of equations (7) and (8) as:

$$f_g[n] = f_g[n-1] + (C_g P_{gI}[n-1] - \xi_g[n-1]) \Delta t \quad (34)$$

$$V_g[n] = V_g[n-1] + (H_g[n-1] + \alpha_g[n-1]) \Delta t \quad (35)$$

$$\tilde{S}_g[n] = \beta_g[n] \quad (36)$$

where C_g and $\xi_g[n]$ are given as [1]:

$$C_g = \frac{f_o}{(2H_g)} \quad (37)$$

$$\xi_g[n] = \frac{C_g}{2\pi f_g[n]} \sum_{\substack{m=1 \\ m \neq g}}^G (B_{gm} V_g[n] V_m[n] \cos(\lambda_{gm}[n])) \quad (38)$$

with f_o being the nominal frequency, H_g being the inertia constant of bus g (see ref. [1]), and B_{gm} being the mutual inductance between buses g and m . Equation (34) provides magnitudes of bus voltages at each time step n . In order to obtain the phases of bus voltages, a power flow analysis is performed at each n :

$$0 = ([\mathbf{Y}[n]] \times [\mathbf{V}[n]])^* \circ [\mathbf{V}[n]] - [\bar{\mathbf{S}}[n]] \quad (39)$$

The main focus of this article is to assess possible impacts of load-side activities (the interconnection of distributed generation units and/or demand response actions) on bus voltages (magnitudes and phases). In this article, load-side activities are carried out under the following assumptions:

- $\mathbf{Y}^*[G \times G] = \tilde{\mathbf{Y}}[G \times G]$: no change in system configuration;
- a load-side activity has a known change in the power injected into bus g as: $\Delta \bar{\mathbf{S}}_g = \Delta P_g + j\Delta Q_g$;

The following procedure provides steps to determine $(\Gamma_{\mathbf{V}})$ at each Δt for each bus.

STEP 1: Identify buses to host load-side activities, and specify G , $\Delta \bar{\mathbf{S}}$, and Δt .

STEP 2: Perform a power flow with f^* , $[\mathbf{Y}]^*$, and $[\bar{\mathbf{S}}]^*$, to obtain $[\tilde{\mathbf{V}}]^*$.

STEP 3: Set $n = 1$ and $g = 1$.

STEP 4: Calculate $f_g[n]$, $\bar{S}_g[n]$, $[\mathbf{Y}[n]]$, then calculate $[\mathbf{V}[n]]$.

STEP 5: Calculate $(\Gamma_{\mathbf{V}})_g$, $((\Gamma_{\mathbf{V}})_g)_{\max}$, and $((\Gamma_{\mathbf{V}})_g)_{\min}$.

STEP 6: **IF** $((\Gamma_{\mathbf{V}})_g)_{\min} \leq (\Gamma_{\mathbf{V}})_g \leq ((\Gamma_{\mathbf{V}})_g)_{\max}$

go to **STEP 7**.

ELSE Declare **Unsurvivable Event**

STOP

STEP 7: **IF** $g + 1 \geq G$:

set $n = n + 1$, $g = 1$, and go to **STEP 4**.

ELSE $g = g + 1$ and go to **STEP 4**.

B. The Test System: BLPC Power System

The voltage survivability analysis is conducted for the Barbados Light & Power Company (BLPC) system that has its nominal frequency $f_o = 50$ Hz. The test system is an isolated 21-bus power system that is located in Barbados, which has its single-line diagram shown in Fig. 1 [1]. Table I lists the rated generation $(P_G)_{\max}$, voltage V_o , active and reactive power demands P_o and Q_o , and power of battery energy storage systems (BESSs) for each bus in the test system.

It should be noted that values of H (in Table I) have been determined as detailed in ref. [11] and ref. [12].

V. RESULTS OF VOLTAGE SURVIVABILITY ANALYSIS

The procedure for performing the voltage survivability analysis was converted into a MATLAB code, which had the data of BLPC power system. Several tests were conducted

Fig. 1. The single-line diagram of the test BLPC power system.

TABLE I
DATA FOR BLPC POWER SYSTEM.

Bus	$(P_G)_{\max}$ [MW]	V_o [kV]	P_o [MW]	Q_o [MVAR]	BESS [MW]	H [sec.]
1	78 (Conv.)	24.9	16.0	7.5	0.0	14.94
2	4.0 (Solar)	24.9	15.0	7.0	0.0	1.82
3	0.0	24.9	18.0	10.0	0.0	2.03
4	0.0	24.9	5.5	3.0	0.0	1.09
5	5.0 (Solar)	24.9	12.5	5.0	0.0	1.44
6	10.0 (Solar)	24.9	18.0	8.0	5.0	1.12
7	0.0	24.9	10.0	7.5	0.0	1.19
8	7.0 (Solar)	24.9	8.0	4.5	4.0	1.15
9	0.0	24.9	11.5	4.5	0.0	1.34
10	0.0	24.9	12.5	5.5	0.0	1.49
11	0.0	24.9	12.5	6.7	0.0	1.48
12	10.0 (Solar)	24.9	5.5	3.0	0.0	1.06
13	0.0	24.9	8.0	4.5	0.0	1.11
14	5.0 (Solar)	24.9	6.6	4.0	4.0	0.98
15	0.0	24.9	2.5	1.0	0.0	0.48
16	15.0 (Conv.)	24.9	16.4	7.0	0.0	2.90
17	0.0	24.9	12.0	6.8	0.0	1.40
18	0.0	24.9	11.0	5.0	0.0	1.33
19	5.0 (Solar)	24.9	1.5	0.5	2.5	0.52
20	0.0	24.9	13.0	8.0	5.0	1.56
21	10.0 (Solar)	24.9	0.0	5.0	5.0	0.30

Conv.: conventional power generation. $S_{\text{base}} = 100$ MVA.

for integrating solar power generation (PV) units, demand response (DR) activities, and interconnecting shunt reactive power compensators. Sample test cases (listed in Table II) are presented and discussed in this paper.

TABLE II
A SUMMARY OF SAMPLE TEST CASES

Bus	Event	ΔP_{Event}	ΔQ_{Event}	$ \bar{\mathbf{S}} $
Bus 4	DR Activity	2.0 MW	0.0 MVAR	8.08 MVA
Bus 3	Capacitor Bank	0.0 MW	-6.0 MVAR	18.44 MVA
Bus 14	BESS Discharge	-3.0 MW	-1.5 MVAR	4.38 MVA
Bus 21	Solar Power	-5.0 MW	0.0 MVAR	0.00 MVA

In order to create a base case for the test power system, the power flow analysis was carried out without any load-side activities. The purpose of this power flow analysis was to obtain bus voltage magnitudes and angles. The obtained bus voltage magnitudes and angles are shown in Fig. 2.

A. Test Case 1: DR Activity on Bus 4

This test case aimed to examine the voltage survivability analysis for a DR activity of increasing the active power

Fig. 2. Base case bus voltage magnitudes and phases for the BLPC power system without any load-side activities. (a) per-unit bus voltage magnitudes ($|V|$), and (b) bus voltage angles (λ).

demands of the load at bus 4. The load at bus 4 was step changed as:

$$P_4 = 5.5 \xrightarrow{t=5s} 7.5 \text{ MW} \quad (40)$$

The estimated system frequency and bus 4 voltage (magnitude and phase) are shown in Fig. 3. The voltage survivability index

Fig. 3. Test case 1 with DR activity at bus 4 with an increase of load demands by 2.0 MW: (a) the system frequency f , (b) the magnitude bus 4 voltage, and (c) the phase of bus 4 voltage.

Γ_V for all buses, along with voltage magnitudes and phases for buses 3 and 5 (connected to bus 4) are shown in Fig. 4.

It could be seen from Fig. 3 (a) that the increase in load demands at bus 4 by 2 MW caused oscillations in the frequency,

Fig. 4. Test case 1 with DR activity at bus 4 with an increase of load demands by 2.0 MW: (a) the voltage survivability index Γ_V for all buses, with $(\Gamma_V)_{\text{System}} = 0.0468$. (b) the voltage magnitudes of buses 3 and 5. (c) the voltage phases of buses 3 and 5.

which settled within stable frequency range. The voltage magnitude and phase of bus 4 (Fig. 3 (b) and (c)) demonstrated oscillations before a stable steady state was reached, and within allowed range of voltage variations. The results in Fig. 3 indicated that the DR activity at bus 4 did not jeopardize the frequency or voltage stability (the new steady-state within stable ranges). The results in Fig. 4 confirmed that the DR activity in bus 4 was a survivable event, as suggested by the index Γ_{V4} , which remained within its boundary values (see Fig. 4 (a)). The results of Test Case 1 were also supported by the minor changes in the voltage magnitudes and phases of buses 3 and 5 (connected to bus 4), where the index Γ_{V3} and Γ_{V5} did not exceed their boundary values. The tested DR activity at Bus 4 caused some bus voltages to suffer oscillations before reaching a new stable steady-state. The results of Test Case 1 demonstrated an encouraging response of the proposed method to an event that did not affect the stability and survivability of the test power system. The results of Test Case 1 can be interpreted as planning a DR activity at bus 4, with an increase of load demands by 2.0 MW, would not jeopardize the stability and voltage survivability of the test power system.

B. Test Case 2: Shunt Capacitor Bank at Bus 3

The objective of this test case was to assess the voltage survivability analysis for interconnecting a shunt capacitor bank to inject 6.0 MVAR at bus 3. This shunt capacitor bank changed the reactive power demands at bus 3 from 10.0 MVAR to 4.0 MVAR. Fig. 5 shows the estimated system frequency and bus 3 voltage (magnitude and phase). Fig. 6 shows the

Fig. 5. Test case 2 with a shunt capacitor bank to inject 6.0 MVAR at bus 3: (a) the system frequency f , (b) the magnitude bus 3 voltage, and (c) the phase of bus 3 voltage.

voltage survivability index Γ_V for all buses, along with voltage magnitudes and phases for bus 4, bus 6, and bus 21 that were connected to bus 3.

The results of Test Case 2 (Fig. 5 and Fig. 6) demonstrate that interconnecting a shunt capacitor bank at bus 3 (to inject 6.0 MVAR) caused minor frequency changes, as shown in Fig. 5 (a). The voltage magnitude and phase of bus 3 (see Fig. 5 (b) and (c)) experienced small oscillations before reaching a stable steady state within the allowed range of voltage variations. The interconnection of the shunt capacitor bank at bus 3 was a survivable event, as indicated by the index Γ_{V3} that did not exceed its boundary values (see Fig. 6 (a)). The voltage survivability of the test power (post the interconnection of the shunt capacitor bank at bus 3) was also supported by the minor changes in the voltage magnitudes and phases of buses 4, 6, and 21 (connected to bus 3), where Γ_{V4} , Γ_{V6} , and Γ_{V21} remained within their boundary values. The results of Test Case 2 were in agreement with those obtained from Test Case 1, planning

Fig. 6. Test case 2 with a shunt capacitor bank to inject 6.0 MVAR at bus 3: (a) the voltage survivability index Γ_V for all buses, with $(\Gamma_V)_{\text{System}} = -0.0114$. (b) the voltage magnitudes of buses 4, 6, and 21. (c) the voltage phases of buses 4, 6, and 21.

an event in a power system could be assessed in terms of its impacts on bus voltages, and system ability to reach a stable steady-state.

C. Test Case 3: Battery Storage System at Bus 14

This test case aimed to assess the voltage survivability analysis for discharging a BESS at bus 14. The BESS discharging adjusted the power demands at bus 14 as:

$$P_{14} = 6.6 \xrightarrow{t=5s} 3.6 \text{ MW} \quad (41)$$

$$Q_{14} = 4.0 \xrightarrow{t=5s} 2.5 \text{ MW} \quad (42)$$

The estimated system frequency and bus 14 voltage (magnitude and phase) are shown in Fig. 7. The voltage survivability index Γ_V for all buses, along with voltage magnitudes and phases for buses 13 and 15 (connected to bus 14) are shown in Fig. 8.

Fig. 7 and Fig. 8 show the results for Test Case 3, which involved discharging a BESS at bus 14. The tested event was created to inject $3.0 + j1.5$ MVA at bus 14, which resulted in significant oscillations in the frequency and V_{14} (magnitude and phase), as shown in Fig. 7 (a), (b), and (c). The magnitude and phase of V_{14} experienced large and sustained oscillations that reached the boundary of their stable range. The BESS discharge at bus 14 pushed the system to the edge of its

Fig. 7. Test case 3 with BESS discharge at bus 14: (a) the system frequency f , (b) the magnitude bus 14 voltage, and (c) the phase of bus 14 voltage.

survivability, as indicated by Γ_{V14} that reached its boundary value (see Fig. 8 (a)). Furthermore, Γ_{V13} and Γ_{V15} changed due to the BESS discharging at bus 14, however, their changes remained within survivability limits. The discharging of a BESS at bus 14 resulted in injecting a significant amount of power relative to load demands at bus 14. As a consequence, BLPC system (the test system) was pushed to its survivability limits, as indicated by the large oscillations in the frequency and V_{14} . This behavior of the test system could be justified based on the bus connections, as bus 14 was only connected to bus 13 and bus 15. Such a bus connection limited the ability of BLPC system to transfer the excess power to other buses and maintain a steady-state operation. The results of Test Case 3 demonstrated agreement with other tests, where planning a BESS installation at bus 14 could be easily evaluated using the proposed voltage survivability analysis.

D. Test Case 4: The Loss of Solar Power at Bus 21

The objective of this test case was to demonstrate the validity of the voltage survivability analysis for examining the impacts of losing a distributed solar energy system at one of the buses in the test system. This test case is created by losing 5.0 MW of solar power generation at bus 21, which had no loads connected to it. Fig. 9 shows the estimated system frequency and bus 21 voltage (magnitude and phase) for Test Case 4. Fig. 10 shows

Fig. 8. Test case 3 with BESS discharge at bus 14: (a) the voltage survivability index Γ_V for all buses, with $(\Gamma_V)_{System} = 0.0842$. (b) the voltage magnitudes of buses 13 and 15. (c) the voltage phases of buses 13 and 15.

the voltage survivability index Γ_V for all buses, along with voltage magnitudes and phases for buses 3 and 7 (connected to bus 21).

Results of Test Case 4 (Fig. 9 and Fig. 10) demonstrate an unsurvivable event, when 5.0 MW of power were lost at bus 21. The loss of solar power triggered significant oscillations in the frequency, V_{21} , V_3 , and V_7 (magnitudes and phases), as shown in Fig. 9 (a), (b), and (c), as well as Fig. 10 (b) and (c). Observed bus voltages experienced large and sustained oscillations that did not allow these voltages to reach new post-event steady-state conditions. The loss of the solar power at bus 21 shifted the test power system into unsurvivable condition, as confirmed by Γ_{V21} that exceeded its boundary value (see Fig. 10 (a)). Test Case 4 involved a total loss of the power generated at bus 21, thus abruptly changing the power flows with other buses. As a result, voltage and frequency went through abrupt variations leading to exceeding the survivability limits. Results of Test Case 4 could be justified based on the bus connections in the test system, where bus 21 had connections with bus 3 and bus 7. This connection of bus 21 indicated a limited ability to transfer power from the system to bus 21 in order to restore a steady-state operation. The results of Test Case 4 demonstrated agreement with other test results, where analyzing an event of losing solar generation at a bus could be evaluated using the

Fig. 9. Test case 4 with a loss of 5.0 MW of solar generation at bus 21: (a) the system frequency f , (b) the magnitude bus 21 voltage, and (c) the phase of bus 21 voltage.

proposed voltage survivability analysis.

A further demonstration for the impacts of changing the power injection on voltage survivability was created at bus 12. The power injected into bus 12 was changed from -6.25 to 6.25 MVA, with $\Delta|S_{12}| = 1.25$ MVA, where $(\Gamma_V)_{12}$ was evaluated for each change. Fig. 11 shows the $(\Gamma_V)_{12}$ with $\Delta|S_{12}|$. One could see from Fig. 11 that large adjustments in $|S_{12}|$ resulted in $(\Gamma_V)_{12}$ exceeding its boundary values. When $(\Gamma_V)_{12}$ exceeded its boundary values, the test system would experience unsurvivable events. Such a behavior could be observed for all buses, however, each bus would have its boundary values for its own survivability index Γ_V .

Results of the two test cases have revealed encouraging performance of the voltage survivability analysis, when used to assess possible impacts of load-side activities on bus voltages in a power system. Analysis results have shown that a load-side activity can affect some buses that are connected to the bus hosting that load-side activity. Such buses have experienced non-zero values of their Γ_V . Tests in this article have presented changes in the power injected into some buses, where such changes can have impacts on the voltage survivability. The voltage survivability analysis has been successful in classifying load-side activities into survivable and unsurvivable events based on the index Γ_V of individual buses. The accuracy and simplicity of the proposed voltage survivability method support

Fig. 10. Test case 4 with a loss of 5.0 MW of solar generation at bus 21: (a) the voltage survivability index Γ_V for all buses, with $(\Gamma_V)_{\text{System}} = 0.1064$. (b) the voltage magnitudes of buses 3 and 7. (c) the voltage phases of buses 3 and 7.

Fig. 11. Impacts of changing the power injected into bus 12 on $(\Gamma_V)_{12}$.

its utilization in power systems.

VI. CONCLUSION

This article has presented the development and performance assessment of a new tool to plan load-side activities in power systems. The proposed tool is based on the voltage survivability analysis, and it defines an index Γ_V based on the difference between pre-activity and post-activity power injection into a bus. The index Γ_V has boundary values that are stated in terms of the mutual admittances between the bus hosting a load-side activity and other buses. This proposed voltage survivability

index has been found simple to calculate, and accurate to quantify the ability of a power system to regain a stable steady-state post a load-side activity. A procedure has been developed to implement the voltage survivability analysis for an isolated power system. The test power system has been selected as Barbados Power System, which has 21 buses with several of them hosting solar power generation units. Several tests have been conducted for load-side activities that are DR actions and interconnecting a shunt capacitor bank. Test results have successfully categorized load-side activities into survivable and unsurvivable events using the index Γ_V . Magnitudes and phases of bus voltages have been collected for each tested case to validate the outcome of the voltage survivability analysis. The accuracy, simplicity, and minor sensitivity to load-side activity support the use of the proposed voltage survivability analysis in power systems.

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